

LABORATORY DIAGNOSIS OF THE LEVEL ACTIVITY OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS.

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Abstract. Chronic hepatitis one of the most dangerous disease. According to the data in the world, about 58 million people are sick with chronic hepatitis C. Approximately one third of those infected in the first six months after infection achieve a spontaneous cure, the remaining 55–85% develop a chronic disease. The virus is transmitted mainly through the blood - through the use of drugs intravenously, during traumatic cosmetic and medical procedures, less often - through sexual contact. Left untreated, hepatitis C can lead to cirrhosis and liver cancer. The most common cause of chronic hepatitis is the hepatitis C virus, it is found in 77.97% of cases of newly diagnosed chronic hepatitis. It infects about 50,000 people a year.

Purpose of the study: to study the level of liver tissue in patients with chronic hepatitis C and, based on the data obtained, develop a new method for assessing the degree of activity of chronic hepatitis.

Material and methods. The study included 60 patients aged 20-44 (average age 30 ± 5) years with clinical sign of chronic hepatitis. According to the activity of the disease, 2 main groups of patients. First group patients with a mild course of the disease ($n=24$), second group patients with severe course ($n=26$). The control group consisted of 10 practically healthy equal children of the same age and sex. Clinical and laboratory examination of patients with chronic hepatitis C was based on the use of clinical, biochemical (determination of serum ALT activity), serological (indication in blood serum by ELISA of antibodies to structural and non-structural proteins of HCV classes IgM and IgG) and molecular biological methods

The predominant HCV genotype in the examined CHC patients was 1b, which was registered in 20 patients(26.3%), 3a and 2a were detected less frequently 20 (28.2%). The level of viral load was determined in 27(45,5%) patients with CHC. In 12 of them, the amount of HCV in the blood was less than 300,000 IU / ml, in 20 - from 300,000 IU / ml to 600,000 IU / ml, and in 5 - over 600,000 IU / ml. It was found that when a pH level of less than 6.76 units was detected in patients. a moderate degree of activity of chronic hepatitis is stated, which corresponds to an IHA of 9-12 points; with pH fluctuations from 6.76 to 7.25

units. with a probability of 95.6% - mild activity of chronic hepatitis with IHA from 4 to 8 points; at a pH value of more than 7.25 units. with a probability of 90.9% - chronic hepatitis with minimal activity of the pathological process, IHA - from 1 to 3 points.

Results. A clear relationship was found between the pH values of liver and the histological activity index in patients with chronic hepatitis C. The results obtained allowed us to develop a new method for assessing the degree of activity of chronic hepatitis in patients with chronic hepatitis C (Method for rapid assessment of the degree of activity of chronic hepatitis in patients with chronic hepatitis C).

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